

The Theme of Ambivalence and Adjustment in Hansda Sowvendra Shekhar's Short Story 'November is the Month of Migrations' in the Age of Migration.

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Abstract: The paper studies the theme of ambivalence and adjustment in migration literature reasoning the short story 'November is the Month of Migrations' by Hansda Sowvendra Shekhar, published in 2015 in his intensely political book of short stories *The Adivasi Will Not Dance*. Writers from different countries present postmodern experiences of greater diversity through their writings. Migration and its outcomes are one such experience presented by the Adivasi writer Shekhar from his own community's experience. The paper examines the individual experience of the story's protagonist Talamai Kisku, a migrant worker from Santhal Pargana, Jharkhand to Namal, the Bardhaman district of West Bengal. It is the economic, political, and cultural circumstances that force an individual or society to move from their native land to new places. In the process of migration, they get involved with different places and people that affect their lives. Talamai gets involved in such circumstances, debates herself, and finally accepts the harsh reality to move on.

Index Terms: migration, ambivalence, adjustment, society.

I. INTRODUCTION

Paul White in his introductory chapter titled *Geography, Literature and Migration* asserts that “We live in what has recently been termed ‘The Age of Migration’. Geographical movement is a crucial human experience.” In Jharkhand, it is not an uncommon phenomenon. Seasonal and permanent migration is reported from the early nineteenth century from the different divisions of Jharkhand. The reasons behind such migrations are economic, political, social, and cultural. It results in new experiences when the migrants are involved in the process of migration. It changes their inner and outer experiences of life. Hansda Sowvendra Shekhar, a doctor and writer of fictional and non-fictional works, and translator of prose and poetry from Santhali, and Hindi into English, writes the experiences of tribes of Jharkhand. In his collection of stories *The Adivasi Will Not Dance*, Shekhar portrays the experiences of Adivasi life especially of the Santhal community. His short story ‘November is the Month of Migrations’ depicts migration as a theme. The theme of migration is extremely common in writings. “The frequency with which the theme appears is not simply a reflection of the realities of human existence but also has an internal literary justification to it.” (White, 1995, p.5)

II. Theme of Ambivalence and Adjustment in Migration Literature

Migration literature deals with the circumstances behind migration, the involvement of the individual, group, or society with new people and new places, and the outcomes. Writings on migrant cultures show the ambivalence between the old and new experiences in the life of the migrants. It is all about life changes. The dislocation of the characters brings new challenges in their life. Sometimes, they are marginalized, exploited, and alienated. The inner conditions of their life are changed. An individual’s life gets affected, and the community falls into an identity crisis. In some contexts, the aspirations of the migrants turn to disillusionment, plurality, and shifting of identities. However, the outcome is the adjustment amidst the ambivalence. The migrants live accepting the plurality, balancing the old and new experiences. Circumstances, borders in all senses, and identities may be changed but the return to the past is felt. In some sense, the exploitation of the individual is adjusted in circumstances like poverty. The individual’s suffering becomes the mark of the identity of that society.

III. The Level of Ambivalence and Adjustment in ‘November is the Month of Migrations’

‘November is the Month of Migrations’ is based on the seasonal migration of the Santhal community of Santhal Pargana of Jharkhand to Namal of Bardhaman district of West Bengal to work in the paddy fields of the landlords. Talamai Kisku is

the central character of the story. Circumstances have forced her to migrate with a group of forty-three people in her community. All the community members are waiting at the station because the train is late for two hours. She leaves the group and is attracted by a Diku (outsider), a Railway Protection Force. He exploits her sexually giving her two cold breads and an amount of fifty rupees.

The story is based on the same theme of ambivalence and adjustment as Stratis Haviars' *When the Tree Sings*, a novel on individual loss, and changes of attitudes in a community, and John Steinbeck's *The Grapes of Wrath* on the human yearning. However the former is based on the author's objective viewpoint, and the latter writings are based on autobiographical experiences. The motive of Shekhar is here to depict the realities faced by women in migration cultures. For this endeavor, he was criticized by his community and the then government of Jharkhand. It may raise the question of negation, but understanding the social, political, and economic context is an urgent need.

Jharkhand is the state of tribes. Santhals, Oraon, Ho, Munda, and other tribes live in this state. Professor Prakash Chandra Deogharia writes that "For over a hundred years, the tribals of Chotanagpur and SanthalPargana regions of Jharkhand, have been steadily migrating out of their homeland in search of livelihood. Because of the development policies of the Government, big dams and industries were established acquiring the lands and forests of the tribal's. The tribals are dependent on land and forests for their livelihood. This usurpation caused a crisis of livelihood for the tribal in Jharkhand, thus the persons displaced were compelled to migrate to urban areas for their bread and butter at very low wages. Women, who play a very important role in bringing up their family and children, are also adversely affected by these development programmes."

Talamai Kisku's migration is one such reason. Though she is Christian she has not got the facilities promised at the time of Christianization by Christian missionaries. She is living in the traditional economic system. During November, the Santhal community leaves the hilly area in search of work in the paddy fields of landlords in Bardhaman district. It is the economic structure that compels the Santhals to leave their homeland. When they leave their homes in the remote villages, they begin to disinherit their own identity and lose their cultural integrity. Poverty shows them the harsh realities of humankind. Talamai's parents, two sisters, and three brothers and one sister-in-law are migrant workers. Her three brothers and sister-in-law have already left for Bardhaman.

She arrives at the station with her parents and one sister to take the train, The train is two hours late. She is hungry and this cursed hunger leads her to the police quarter at the station. There is a Diku (outsider), a Railway Protection Force, who tries to attract her by showing a bread pakora. Here is found the level of ambivalence that is the conflict, the duality in the mind. Migration cultures drive an individual to such circumstances. She is the victim of dislocation. When dislocation begins in a particular community, outer forces hazard the self-identity. The protagonist is in a crisis- "Talamai

debates if she should follow...” (Shekar,2015, p.40). Tribes are regarded as the most cultured and their sense of honour is also not so degraded that a single piece of bread can attract her to give her body. Bu the next moment Talamai “decides to” be involved in the fulfillment of the Diku’s desire. It is the outcome of migration that brings an individual to a contradictory situation. Thus, migration drives one to be exploited in circumstances of economic, political, and social. The individual identity is generalized when the Diku says, “Saali, you Santhal women are made for this only. You are good!” Such complex phenomena affect the individual, group, or societal identity that are common theme in migration.

What next? Protest will not be Talamai’s recourse. She accepts the reality silently- “Then he gives Talamai two pieces of cold bread pakora and a fifty-rupee note and walks away. She re-ties her saya and lungi and stuffs the fifty-rupee note into her blouse” (Shekhar, 2015 p.42) It is as if adjusted in her inner soul. She is trapped in a mechanism as the whole clan- “And she knows that on their way to Namal, Santhal Women do this work for food and money at the railway station, too” (Shekar,2015, p.40) Their destination has been altered as they are the victims of the cultural, political, economical and social circumstances. It can not be denied that exploitation does not affect the identity of individuals, groups, or society. However, poverty compels them to accept it naturally.

IV. Conclusion

Thus, Shekhar has depicted the experiences of the seasonal migration of the Santhal community using a fictional form of literature. Talamai’s journey from ‘debate’ to adjustment is noteworthy here. Such experiences are rare in migration literature. Shekhar’s study of migration and its outcomes is exceptional. Writers write about various experiences on migration, but Shekhar is courageous. Social-scientist may ask the author about the reliability of the fact, but when a writer is writing about his community obviously, he knows the social, political, and economic circumstances of the time.

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